

strip of cloth were placed in the center of the top layer of each cylinder. Infestation was sustained for 10 wk, during which two generations of AGM developed.

AGM larvae bored through the entire depth (10 cm) of susceptible CO 44; infestation depth was 7 cm in resistant CO 32 (see table). Infestation was higher in the first three sections, with maximum infestation in the top layer, for both varieties. Infestation at 10 cm of susceptible CO 44 was higher than that at 7 cm of resistant CO 32. □

Depth of infestation and percentage of grains damaged by AGM in resistant and susceptible rice varieties. Tamil Nadu, India.

Depth (cm)	Grain damage ^a (%)	
	CO 32 (resistant)	CO 44 (susceptible)
1	32.7 (34.92) f	37.7 (37.91) e
2	2.9 (9.17) e	4.2 (11.92) d
3	1.7 (7.70) d	2.6 (9.01) c
4	0.9 (5.87) c	0.8 (5.32) b
5	0.4 (3.91) b	0.7 (5.07) b
6	0.2 (2.95) ab	0.3 (3.38) a
7	0.1 (2.56) ab	0.2 (3.09) a
8	0.0 (1.81) a	0.2 (2.89) a
9	0.0 (1.81) a	0.1 (2.70) a
10	0.0 (1.81) a	0.2 (2.89) a

^a Mean of 3 replications. Figures in parentheses are arcsin percentage transformed values. In a column, values followed by a common letter do not differ significantly (P=0.05) by DMRT.

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CROP AND RESOURCE MANAGEMENT

Soil microbiology and biological N fertilizer

Effect of nitrogen, phosphorus, and cropping method on azolla productivity

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We studied the effect of N, P, and method of azolla culture on azolla productivity in irrigated lowlands during 1983 wet season (Jun-Oct). Soil was sandy clay with pH 6.7; 286, 27, 341 kg available NPK/ha.

The experiment was in a split-plot design with three replications. Main plots were combinations of 0, 50, and 100 kg N/ha and 0, 11, and 22 kg P/ha; subplots were three methods of growing azolla with transplanted rice: monocropping, intercropping, and dual cropping.

Jaya rice was transplanted at 20- × 10-cm spacing 18 Jul. Fresh *Azolla pinnata* R. Br. at 3 t/ha was inoculated to monocrop and dual-crop plots 20 d before transplanting rice and to intercrop plots 1 d after transplanting.

Azolla was manually incorporated 2 times before transplanting in monocrop plots, 2 times after transplanting in intercrop plots, and 2 times each before and after transplanting in dual-crop plots. N as urea was applied in two equal splits, at transplanting and 30 d after transplanting; P as single superphosphate was applied basally; K as muriate of potash was applied basally at 42 kg K/ha to all plots.

Application of 50 kg N/ha had no adverse effect on yield of fresh azolla, but application of 100 kg N/ha significantly reduced azolla yield in the dual-crop plots (Table 1, 2).

In dual cropping, remnant azolla that

Table 1. Effect of N, P, and method of cultivation on azolla.^a Bangalore, India, 1983 wet season.

Treatment	Dry matter (%)	Nutrient content in dry matter (%)			Yield (t/ha)		N contribution (kg N/ha)	
		N	P	K	Total	Per day	Total	Per day
N (kg/ha)								
0	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.2	24.9	0.8	36.1	1.1
50	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.1	24.1	0.8	34.6	1.1
100	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.1	21.8	0.7	33.1	1.1
LSD (P 0.05)	ns	ns	ns	ns	2.2	0.1	ns	ns
P (kg/ha)								
0	6.1	2.2	0.1	1.1	23.6	0.7	34.6	1.1
11	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.1	22.4	0.7	33.7	1.1
22	6.9	2.1	0.2	1.2	24.9	0.8	35.5	1.1
LSD (P 0.05)	0.10	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns	ns
Monocropping	6.9	2.2	0.2	1.3	19.8	1.0	30.0	1.5
Intercropping	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.1	15.6	0.5	22.4	0.8
Dual cropping	6.8	2.1	0.2	1.0	35.4	0.7	51.4	1.0
LSD (P 0.05)	0.1	ns	0.0	0.1	1.4	0.0	3.4	0.1
LSD (P 0.01)	0.1	ns	ns	0.1	1.8	0.1	4.5	0.1
General mean	6.8	2.2	0.2	1.1	23.6	0.7	34.6	1.1

^a ns = not significant.

had been mixed with fertilizer N during soil incorporation was retained as seed for further multiplication. In monocrop and intercrop plots, fresh azolla was inoculated. Adverse effects of more than 50 kg N/ha would be reduced by minimizing mixing of fertilizer N and azolla or by seeding fresh azolla for further multiplication.

The poor response of azolla to applied P may be due to the high available P in the soil and its increased availability under flooded conditions.

Monocropping for 20 d and dual cropping for 50 d resulted in higher yields of fresh azolla, contributing more N/day, dry matter content, and K

Table 2. Effect of N and cultivation method interaction on yield of fresh azolla, Bangalore, India, 1983 wet season.

N (kg/ha)	Total yield of fresh azolla (t/ha)			
	Monocropping	Intercropping	Dual cropping	Mean
0	21.0	16.0	37.8	24.9
50	19.8	15.4	37.1	24.1
100	18.5	15.6	31.5	21.8
Mean	19.8	15.6	35.4	23.6
LSD (P=0.05)	2.4 ^a	3.0 ^b		

^aBetween 2 methods of cultivation at same level of N. ^bBetween 2 N levels in same cultivation method.

content of dry matter. Monocrop azolla did not experience any competition with rice. Intercrop azolla suffered

considerable competition with rice for all growth factors, in particular light and nutrients. □

Physiology and plant nutrition

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields

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We studied the effect of age of seedling and removal of leaf on rice grain and straw yields during kharif 1988, at the Seed Farm (23.5° N, 89.0° E, and 9.75 mean sea level). Treatments were three seedling ages and four leaf removal levels, in a split-plot design with four replications.

Soil was clayey loam (0.61% organic C, 0.59% total N, 14 kg available P/ha, 208 kg available K/ha, and pH 6.8). Fertilizer was 40-50-50 kg NPK/ha

applied at plowing and 50 kg N/ha applied 30 d after transplanting (DT). IR8 seedlings at 21, 28, and 35 d after seeding were transplanted 20 Jul at 25-×

15-cm spacing, four seedlings/hill. Leaves were removed (0, 25, 50, and 100%) 1 mo after transplanting in 7.5-× 2.0-m subplots.

Seedling age did not significantly affect grain and straw yields. Grain and straw yields decreased with increased leaf removal (see table). □

Effect of seedling age and leaf removal on rice grain and straw yields of IR8. West Bengal, India, 1988.

Seedling age (d)	Yield (t/ha)									
	No leaves removed		25% of leaves removed		50% of leaves removed		100% of leaves removed		Mean	
	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw	Grain	Straw
21	4.8	5.0	3.6	4.0	3.6	4.0	2.8	3.6	3.7	4.1
28	4.4	4.7	4.4	5.0	4.0	4.5	3.8	4.7	4.2	4.7
35	4.5	4.9	3.7	4.2	3.2	3.5	3.1	3.3	3.6	4.0
Mean	4.6	4.8	3.9	4.4	3.6	4.0	3.2	3.9	—	—
LSD (0.05)										
Leaf removal		0.7	grain	0.7	straw					

Influence of potassium and kinetin on protein partitioning in rice

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We examined protein partitioning in rice, using short-duration Triveni in a summer 1987 field experiment at Karamana (8.5° N, 77.9° E, and 29 m above sea level). Soil of the experimental field was sandy loam, pH 4.5, with 84.3, 13.6, 63.8 ppm available NPK.

Treatments, a factorial combination of four potassium levels (0, 14.5, 29.1, 58.1) and four kinetin spray treatments, are given in Table 1. The experiment was laid out in a randomized block design with three replications.

K as KCl was applied 50% basal and 50% at panicle initiation; 70 kg N and